
Book Review

Unveiling the Magic: Mastering the Art of Teaching Poetry

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Book details:

The first edition of the book was released in the year 2024, with an ISBN: 978-93-6252-965-7. The book has been published, printed and distributed by Selfypage Developers Pvt. Ltd. Chikkamagaluru, Karnataka. Imprint; IIP Iterative International Publishers. Email sales@iipbooks.com. The MRP of the book is Rs. 250 and it is available in Amazon. The book contains 10 pages in the Introduction part and 102 pages with the valuable inputs of research-oriented teaching of the art of poetry.

About the Author:

Dr. Sonia Abraham currently serves as the Head of the English Department at Delhi Public School Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh. She has a distinguished educational background with a Master's in Education, M. Phil. in English and a Ph.D. in English literature, with a two decades of teaching experience. Dr. Sonia Abraham has received several prestigious awards during her illustrious educational career. To mention a few, she has received the prestigious Shiksha Bhushan Puraskar 2023, from CED India and Edvishan Education Excellence Award. She was recognised with the Global Teachers Award by CED AND GTE in 2020. She has earned the title of Best Teacher Award from Delhi Public School Bilaspur and Rotary International Club Bilaspur in 2013 & 201.

Review of the book:

Unveiling the Magic: Mastering the Art of Teaching Poetry is an apt title of the book by the author Dr. Sonia Abraham. It's a sheer pleasure to go through the book where each page unveils the minutest details about the Art of Poetry and secondly the Science behind to know the technique of teaching poetry. The methodology and in-depth analysis of how to understand the different forms and nuances of poetry, to interpret and enjoy poetry as a reader, student, teacher, poet, admirer or critic is dealt so vividly with apt and ample examples that it not only creates magic but also provides useful information about poetry.

Diving into the world of poetry in the well-crafted and insightful book weaved by the author explores the new regions of poetry through the captivating and enriching content provided throughout the book with a pragmatic approach. It will certainly open up new vistas of research in the genre of poetry. The book provides a detailed and insightful exploration in a systematic method providing aspiring students with accessible pathways to mastering the art of poetry. This book offers invaluable perspectives and innovative strategies for teaching poetry with creativity and passion.

Dr. Sonia Abraham brings out the beauty of poetry in a broad spectrum irrespective of lingual, cultural and geographical barriers. In a nutshell, it's absolutely a magical experience to go through the book and I recommend that every student, teacher and lover of poetry should read this immensely useful book. Wishing Dr. Sonia Abraham and her book a great success. May God bless her with many more accolades so that she continues her creative journey to reach the zenith.